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7 Analyze

Without self citations

4 Analyze

IJIMS terindeks scopus Q1

The screenshot shows the homepage of the Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies. The header features the journal's title in large, bold, black letters on a yellow background, with the ISSN numbers (p-ISSN 2089-1490 and e-ISSN 2406-825X) to the right. Below the header is a purple navigation bar with links for HOME, ABOUT, LOGIN, REGISTER, SEARCH, CURRENT, ARCHIVES, and ANNOUNCEMENTS. The main content area is white and contains the following text:

Home > [Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies](#)

Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies

Postgraduate Program IAIN Salatiga, Indonesia

Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies has the perspectives of humanities and social sciences. This journal also has programs aimed at bridging the gap between the textual and contextual approaches to Islamic Studies; and solving the dichotomy between 'orthodox' and 'heterodox' Islam. The two were linked: the textual tradition showed that Islam was, as well as a set of religious tenets, a way of approaching the practical economic and social challenges of life. So, this journal invites the intersection of several disciplines and scholars. In other words, its contributors borrowed from a range of disciplines, including the humanities and social sciences.

IJIMS, published twice a year (June and December), always places Islam and Muslim in the central focus of academic inquiry and invites any discussions as the aim and scopes.

IJIMS is a member of Crossref.org since 2015, so each article has its unique DOI number.

IJIMS has been indexed in SCOPUS since August 2017, ACI, Index Islamicus and [more](#).

IJIMS has been granted National Accreditation (A) from Indonesian Directorate General of Higher Education

On the right side of the page, there is a vertical menu with the following items: Author Guideline, Publication Ethics, Focus & Scope, Editorial Team, Peer Review process, Contact Us, Indexed in, and Author fees. At the bottom right, there is a logo for IJIMS School of Journal.

**13 Agustus 2017:
Accepted**

Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies

Open Access

Scopus coverage years: from 2011 to 2020

Publisher: State Institute of Islamic Studies (IAIN) Salatiga

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1.0

SJR 2019

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SNIP 2019

0.468

[CiteScore](#) [CiteScore rank & trend](#) [Scopus content coverage](#)

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Q1

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Mengenal Scopus

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Scopus

Semua jurnal yang tercakup dalam database Scopus, terlepas dari siapa mereka diterbitkan, **ditinjau setiap tahun** untuk memastikan **standar kualitas tinggi dipertahankan**. Pencarian di Scopus juga mencakup pencarian database paten. Scopus memberikan empat jenis ukuran kualitas untuk setiap judul; Yaitu h-Index, CiteScore, SJR (SCImago Journal Rank) dan SNIP (Source Normalized Impact per Paper).

Semua karena scopus

Mediadinamika.com -- Pada awal tahun 2017 Kementerian Ri-set dan Teknologi me-ngeluarkan Per-men-- ristekdikti Nomor 20 tahun 2017 ten--tang Pemberian Tunjangan Pro-fesi Dosen dan Tunjangan Ke-hor-matan Pro--fessor.

Pada Pasal 4 Per-men-ris-tek-dik-ti ter-sebut, antara lain, disebutkan do-sen yang memiliki jenjang aka-demik Lek-tor Kepala wajib memublikasikan 3 (tiga) hasil penelitian atau karya ilmiah-nya pada jurnal nasional terakreditasi atau minimal 1 (satu) karya ilmiah pada jur-nal internasional. **Kalau tidak, tunja-ngan profesinya akan dihen-tikan.**

Tawa dan tangis karena scopus

Sementara itu, pada Pasal 8 disebut-kan dosen yang me-mi-lik-i jabatan aka-de-mik atau fungsional guru besar (pro-fes-sor) wajib memublikasikan 3 (tiga) karya ilmiahnya pada jurnal inter-na--sio-nal atau 1 (satu) karya ilmiah pada jurnal interna-sional bereputasi, **masing-ma-sing da-lam kurun waktu 3 (tiga) tahun..**

Reaksi bermunculan atas terbitnya Permenristekdikti tersebut, terutama dari kalangan dosen. Sebagian dosen menilai persyaratan dalam peraturan tersebut sulit dipenuhi. Pasalnya, jangan-kana pada jurnal ilmiah internasional, memublikasikan karya ilmiah **pada jurnal ilmiah nasional terakreditasi** pun sulit dilakukan, karena saat ini **jumlah jurnal ilmiah nasional terakreditasi sangat terbatas dibandingkan dengan jumlah dosen perguruan tinggi di Indonesia.**

Apalagi, setiap dosen diharuskan melakukan publikasi minimal 3 (tiga) karya ilmiahnya pada jurnal ilmiah nasional terakreditasi tersebut.

Persoalan ma-kin be-rat, ter-utama pada dosen yang me-ngajar pada program studi atau bi-dang ilmu ter-tentu, yang jurnal ilmiah na--sional pada bidang ilmu itu amat lang-ka, apalagi jur-nal ilmiah interna-sional. Reak--si dari pihak lain pun muncul. Ka-bar-nya, DPR, khususnya Ko-misi X, me-minta pemerin-tah agar meng-kaji ulang pe--raturan yang dianggap mem-beratkan ka-langan pen-didik pada per-guruan tinggi tersebut.

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2. Setengah hati, agak suka nulis atau males nulis tapi mau nggak mau harus publish di scopus untuk syarat lulus S3 terutama di Indonesia :)
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Hantu scopus lah
Scopus, mampus lah.

Flow of publication

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Editor

Reviewer 1

Reviewer 2, 3, 4

My paper

Most scientists regarded the new streamlined peer-review process as 'quite an improvement.'

Reviewing flow chart

Week 2

Assign to Associate Editor

Editor in Chief
Co-Editor in Chief

No/Reject

Associate Editor

Check for:

1. Suitability 『 Scope/Objectives 』
2. Originality
3. Classification
4. Soundness

Week 3

Yes/Assign

Reviewer 1
Reviewer 2
(Reviewer 3)

Check for:

1. Methods, Statistics
2. Results consistency
3. Figures
4. Introduction/ Discussion
5. References

Week 5-6

Editor in Chief
Co-Editor in Chief

Associate Editor

Recommendation/
Check Revision

Week 6-8

FINAL DECISION

Author for revision

cek focus n scope, novelty, theoretical contribution, similarity check

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The Stages of Revision

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acceptance

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156 Naskah yang belum diapa-apain

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Video as Educational Multimedia to Teach English Speaking

Novia Fajar Masyitoh¹, Noor Malihah¹, Faizal Risdianto¹ and Agung Guritno¹

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[Journal of Physics: Conference Series, Volume 1339, International Conference Computer Science and Engineering \(IC2SE\) 26–27 April 2019, Padang, Indonesia](#)

Citation Novia Fajar Masyitoh *et al* 2019 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 1339 012118

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to develop an educational multimedia in the form of video as one of media to teach speaking. Research and development design is used to produce an educational multimedia entitled *Nqinaqaris Narsis*. Procedures of this research includes identification students and

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Research Article

The use of drama to develop English speaking autonomous learning

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Faizal Risdianto^{1,*}, Sari Famularsih¹, Setia Rini¹, Ahmad Mifdlol Muthohar¹

1: IAIN Salatiga, Indonesia

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Abstract

For several years there has been an appreciation and huge awareness pertaining to the importance autonomy of learners and the role of individual and group learners in leading their process of learning inside and outside the classroom. Nevertheless, in real teaching and learning process, it is not always visible how to encourage and develop learners dealing with this role, and how to ensure they are ready to perform it. The topic of autonomy of learners is widely discussed and acknowledged among social scientists and observers but perhaps to its complex and myriad characteristics, the autonomy of learners has not been studied widely up to present day. To fill this gap, this qualitative research was conducted to investigate the use of drama to build autonomous English learning towards the students of International class program of IAIN Salatiga batch 2018. They are able to develop their potential in maximum way and be able to learn together in their peer learning group. The second, from the given questionnaire's answers, dealing with the strength of the use of drama in improving student's autonomous learning, it can be seen that there are 16 students who felt that drama performance can improve students' speaking ability, mastery of vocabulary and boost their self-confidence. Pertaining to the weakness of the use of drama in building autonomous learning there are 17 students who said that there is no weakness in the use of drama to build autonomous learning.

Keywords drama autonomous learning english speaking skills

Published 2019-09-23 Publisher EAI

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Proceedings of the International Seminar on Recent Language, Literature, and Local Cultural Studies (BASA 2018)

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Authors

Faizal Risdianto, Sumarlam Sumarlam, Noor Malihah

Corresponding Author

Faizal Risdianto

Available Online November 2018.

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2020	349 documents
2019	305 documents
2018	370 documents
2017	319 documents
2016	189 documents
2015	126 documents

7 tips jitu menulis artikel jurnal

tips menulis jurnal dari Dr..Tole Sutikno, (Universitas Ahmad Dahlan), dalam menembus jurnal bereputasi Internasional, yaitu:

1. Ketahui Pangsa Pasar

Sebelum Anda menulis jurnal, hal pertama yang perlu Anda pikirkan adalah menentukan sasarannya, kepada siapa jurnal tersebut Anda tujukan. Penting untuk Anda ketahui terkait minat pembaca, ketahui apa-apa yang paling diminati oleh kebanyakan pembaca dan ketika Anda menulis – ingatlah calon pembacanya.

2. A Good Manuscript

Pembuatan manuscript jurnal yang baik akan memudahkan pembaca dalam memahami isinya. Perlu Anda cermati dua hal penting agar pembuatan manuscript dapat optimal yaitu CONTENT dan PRESENTATION.

Content jurnal yang Anda buat perlu dipikirkan mengenai kemanfaatannya di masyarakat secara umum. Jika sudah memiliki kemanfaatan yang tinggi, tuliskan dalam bentuk narasi yang semenarik mungkin.

Kesalahan umum:

- Kurang menulis kalimat secara menarik, ringkas dan jelas dengan **kalimat laras ilmiah**;
- Krang memaparkan **masalah penelitian** (*research gap*) secara jelas;
- Kurang memanfaatkan **rujukan primer dan terkini** untuk menggambarkan posisi keilmuan terkini (*state of the art*) dalam kajian pustaka;
- Sering memuat "kajian pustakawan", bukan kajian pustaka, bahkan beberapa kalimat "**kehilangan**" rujukan.
- Kurang memaparkan **perkembangan yang relevan disertai data dan informasi terkini** untuk membentuk fondasi bagi riset yang dilakukan;
- Kurang menggambarkan **kekuatan dan kelemahan** pencapaian dari riset-riset sebelumnya;
- Dalam menuliskan acuan (rujukan) **tidak mengikuti sistem acuan** baku
- Perkembangan terkini menuntut artikel ilmiah yang semakin sederhana sehingga kajian pustaka tidak dituliskan sebagai bagian terpisah namun dimasukkan **dalam pendahuluan, metode dan pembahasan**;

What is Novelty?

1. It is some thing **new or modified** from previous findings.
2. It may create, develop, add, complete or give new alternatives of theory, method, formula, model or other forms in **scientific matter**.
3. Novelty must be **original**.

3. Sering Berlatih Menulis Jurnal

Perlu Anda ketahui bahwa kemampuan menulis jurnal bukanlah dari bakat semata namun lebih mengarah ke skill. Skill dalam penulisan akan semakin terasah jika frekuensi penulisan semakin tinggi. Jadi tidak ada alasan 'Bosan' dalam menulis jurnal ilmiah ini. Menulis membutuhkan skill yang selalu terasah.

4. Buatlah Tulisan yang termudah

Paper yang published di jurnal Internasional bereputasi tidak selamanya terkait dengan teknologi canggih dan mutakhir saja. Akan tetapi dengan melakukan inovasi-inovasi dalam aplikasi teknologi lamapun juga sangat berpeluang. Namun perlu Anda ketahui bahwa yang memiliki peluang tertinggi untuk published adalah yang *pertama menulis tentang sesuatu*

5. **Buatlah Reviewer tertarik dengan Paper Anda**

Membuat tertarik pembaca paper adalah penting, namun membuat reviewer tertarik membaca paper Anda adalah jauh lebih penting, karena tidak ada yang membaca paper Anda lebih teliti dari reviewer.

Akan lebih menarik lagi jika paper yang Anda buat menggunakan referensi dari hasil penelitian reviewer (Ini mungkin lebih tepatnya hanya mengarah ke politis). Tapi tidak masalah asalkan benar-benar mendukung paper yang Anda buat tadi.

Lack of novelty: Salah satu alasan utama rejection

What is Novelty?

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et al. (1982), there are four categories of classification in analyzing errors, i.e. linguistic category classification, surface strategy taxonomy, comparative taxonomy, and communicative effect taxonomy. Among those ways of classifying errors, surface strategy taxonomy is a preferred way to know the types of errors the students make as well as leading them to unlock the factors beyond those errors.

Formerly, there have been several studies employing EA in analyzing second language learners' errors in writing carried out (Mungungu, 2010; Herlinawati, 2011; Wahyudi, 2012). However, none of those studies analyze the learners' errors according to surface strategy taxonomy and investigates the reasons beyond those revealed errors. Actually, Herlinawati (2011) employed surface strategy taxonomy to do the error analysis but she stopped at revealing they type of errors and the most common errors only. Meanwhile, Mungungu (2010) and Wahyudi (2012) used linguistic category to classify the errors revealed. Similar to Herlinawati (2011, they also did not try to explore what lies beyond those errors. Therefore, this present study is conducted to unlock the area beyond the errors that learners made in their writing. It involves Indonesian Junior high school studies English in a learning course as the participants.)

Comment [L3]: This is best practice

1.1 Literature Review

Through this literature review, some information is given to assist readers in having better understanding of what this paper is discussing. Some concept, theories, and related studies dealing with Second Language writing, errors, and Error Analysis are included and presented in the following sections.

a. *Second Language Writing*

Bridges et al. (1984) defined writing as the phase in where a basic draft of a

Preparing Published Articles

The general structure of a full article

- Title
 - Abstract
 - Keywords
 - Main text (IMRAD)
 - Introduction
 - Methods
 - Results
 - And
 - Discussions
 - Acknowledgement
 - Reference
 - Supplementary materials
- Make them easy for indexing and searching!
(informative, attractive, effective)
- Journal space is precious. Make the article as brief as possible. If clarity can be achieved in ***n*** words, never use ***n+1***.
-

Contoh judul yang menarik

Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization 76 (2010) 805–820

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

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How 'Islamic' is Islamic Banking?

Feisal Khan*

Dept. of Economics, Hobart and William Smith Colleges, 300 Pulteney Street, Geneva, NY 14456, United States

ARTICLE INFO

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G21

N25

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Islamic Banking

Murabaha

ABSTRACT

Islamic Banks hold well over US \$700 billion in assets and are growing at over 15% p.a. Islamic Banking and Finance (IBF) involves wider ethical and moral issues than simply 'interest-free' transactions. Its advocates argue that these make it more economically efficient than conventional banking and promote greater economic equity and justice. To what extent, then, do actual Islamic Banking practices live up to the ideal, and how different are they from conventional banking? A preliminary investigation shows that, three decades after its introduction, there remain substantial divergences between IBF's ideals and its practices, and much of IBF still remains functionally indistinguishable from conventional banking. This runs counter to claims by IBF advocates that it would rapidly differentiate itself from conventional banking. However, despite not providing an alternative to conventional banking and finance, IBF does strengthen a distinctly Islamic identity by providing the appropriate Islamic terminology for *de facto* conventional financial transactions.

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Dear Register Editor,

We would like to submit an original research article entitled “xxxxxx-” for consideration by Register Journal. We confirm that this work is original and has not been published elsewhere, nor is it currently under consideration for publication elsewhere.

In this paper, we report on XXXXX. This is significant because it can be a guidance for further research related to the professional Development programs for ELT in the field of technology.

We believe that this manuscript is appropriate for publication by REGISTER JOURNAL because it contains the issues related to technology integration in language teaching.

Our manuscript has the newest perspective of reflection as a media for the teachers improving their metacognitive awareness in XXXXX.

The findings provide a step by step teacher's reflection in realizing each aspect of XXXX. These finding are useful for the government to establish professional development workshops in the technology of educational field and essential for the teacher to design the lesson dealing with technology integration.

We have no conflicts of interest to disclose.

Please address all correspondence concerning this manuscript to me at XXXX@MAIL.AC.ID. Thank you for your consideration of this manuscript.

Sincerely,

AUTHOR 1

AUTHOR 2

AUTHOR 3

6. Hindari Plagiarisme

Sebaik apapun karya ilmiah yang Anda tulis, jika hasil dari copy/paste karya orang lain pasti tidak akan mendapatkan apresiasi dari khalayak umum. Bahkan copy/paste dari hasil karya Anda sendiri yang sudah publish-pun masih dianggap plagiat. Maka dari itu, sebisa mungkin hindarilah tindakan yang merendahkan diri sendiri ini.

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Keindahan tulisan tanpa kehilangan isi yang terkandung di paper Anda sangat membutuhkan adanya koreksi secara terus-menerus. Semakin sering Anda lakukan koreksi maka akan semakin berkualitas paper yang Anda buat.

Ternyata untuk membuahakan jurnal yang terindeks di SCOPUS atau bereputasi Internasional membutuhkan waktu yang cukup panjang jika belum berpengalaman. Namun pengalaman itu pasti akan Anda peroleh jika tidak bosan-bosannya menyempatkan diri untuk terus menulis.

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